

Tracing the History of Carbon, Nitrogen, and Oxygen in the Milky Way

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Abstract

Carbon, nitrogen, and oxygen (CNO) are the most abundant elements in the Universe after hydrogen and helium, playing a key role in stellar evolution and the emergence of life. The DAINA project, “*The history of C, N, and O in the Galaxy*”, a collaboration between the Nicolaus Copernicus Astronomical Center (Polish Academy of Sciences) and the Institute of Theoretical Physics and Astronomy (Vilnius University), aims to provide a comprehensive and homogeneous analysis of CNO abundances across all major Galactic stellar populations. By combining new spectroscopic observations with data from previous and upcoming large spectroscopic surveys and applying robust calibration methods, the project will trace the chemical enrichment of CNO over time and across the Milky Way. Linking abundances with stellar ages, evolutionary stages, and orbital information will allow us to study the effects of stellar migration and internal mixing, offering new insights into the chemodynamical evolution of the Galaxy.

1 Introduction

Apart from hydrogen and helium, produced in primordial nucleosynthesis shortly after the Big Bang, carbon, nitrogen, and oxygen are the three most abundant elements in the Universe. These elements are essential for life as we know it and play a crucial role in the basic chemistry of extraterrestrial environments. They are key constituents of molecules currently considered biomarkers in exoplanetary atmospheres (e.g. CO₂, H₂O, CH₄, and N₂O, see Madhusudhan 2019). Thus, a better understanding of the origin and history of CNO elements has far-reaching implications for the search for life beyond Earth.

However, the observed surface abundances of these elements in stars are shaped not only by the chemical environment at birth, but also by stellar evolutionary processes. As low- and intermediate-mass stars evolve off the main sequence and ascend the red giant branch, their convective envelopes deepen, bringing nuclear-processed

material to the surface. The first dredge-up mixes hydrogen-burning products upward, typically decreasing surface carbon and increasing nitrogen, while leaving oxygen largely unchanged (Iben 1965). In addition, extra mixing processes, such as thermohaline convection and rotation-induced instabilities (Charbonnel & Lagarde 2010), can further alter surface abundances, particularly after the luminosity bump on the red giant branch. Accounting for these stellar effects is essential to disentangle intrinsic Galactic chemical trends from evolutionary modifications.

The aim of this project is to conduct a comprehensive, homogeneous, and precise analysis of CNO abundances in a large sample of stars spanning the main Galactic populations. By combining chemical abundances, stellar ages, and orbital information, we will study not only the chemical enrichment history of the Milky Way but also the imprint of stellar evolution on surface compositions. This approach allows us to investigate local CNO enrichment as a function of Galactocentric radius and to explore the impact of stellar activity on internal mixing processes, which remain poorly constrained.

Overall, this study will provide a detailed picture of CNO evolution in both stars and the Galaxy, offering critical constraints for models of stellar and Galactic chemical evolution, and providing insight into how the elements crucial for life are distributed across stars and Galactic environments.

2 Methods

Our sample combines new spectra obtained at the Moletai Astronomical Observatory with publicly available data from several spectroscopic surveys, including GALAH (De Silva et al. 2015), APOGEE (Holtzman et al. 2015), and Gaia-ESO (Gilmore et al. 2012). A set of reference stars with precisely known stellar parameters is employed to ensure the reliability of abundances derived from the new spectra. The same reference stars are also used to calibrate stellar parameters and improve the precision of abundances from large surveys, following methods developed in our previous work. Accurate stellar parameters further allow us to estimate stellar ages with a precision of approximately 10% using isochronal fitting methods.

We selected for observation FGK-type stars with visual magnitudes $V \leq 8$ and declination $\delta \geq 10^\circ$. Field stars were drawn from the Tycho-2 catalogue (Høg et al. 2000), while cluster stars were taken from van Groeninge et al. (2023) and Hunt & Reffert (2024). In addition, we observed a series of reference stars including the Gaia-FGK benchmarks (Jofré et al. 2018) and metal-poor stars from the TITANS (Giribaldi et al. 2021, 2023), thus covering a wide range of effective temperatures, metallicities, and evolutionary stages. These stars will be used to place the analysis of all targets on a homogeneous reference scale.

Spectral analysis is performed using DAOSPEC (Stetson & Pancino 2008), MOOG, and Turbospectrum v.2019 (Plez 2012). Solar abundances are adopted from Grevesse et al. (2007), and 1D MARCS model atmospheres are used (Gustafsson et al. 2008). The atomic and molecular data are taken from the Gaia-ESO linelist (Heiter et al. 2021).

Oxygen abundances are derived from the single forbidden line at 6300.3 Å, which is reliable and consistent between 1D and 3D models (Amarsi et al. 2016). Carbon abundances are calculated from C₂ Swan bands at 5135 Å and 5635 Å, while the isotopic ratio $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ is obtained from the feature at 8003 Å. Nitrogen abundances are derived from $^{12}\text{C}^{14}\text{N}$ molecular bands in the ranges 6470 Å to 6490 Å and 7990 Å to 8000 Å.

To contextualise these measurements, Fig. 1 shows the predicted distribution of surface [C/N] ratios under two different stellar mixing schemes from Lagarde et al. (2019) (left panel). The right panel illustrates how the $^{12}\text{C}/^{13}\text{C}$ ratio is affected by thermohaline and rotation-induced mixing after the first dredge-up. These models highlight the typical impact of the first dredge-up and subsequent extra mixing on surface abundances, providing a reference framework for interpreting our measured values.

In addition, we will determine stellar masses and ages using UniDAM (Mints & Hekker 2018) and SPInS (Lebreton & Reese 2020). To account for radial migration, we adopt the method developed in Dantas et al. (2025), combined with precise parallaxes and proper motions from the upcoming Gaia Data Release 4.

Figure 1: Stellar mixing effects on surface abundances of our sample. The left panel shows the histogram of [C/N] ratios under two different mixing schemes from Lagarde et al. (2019), while the right panel shows the predicted ¹²C/¹³C ratios.

3 Conclusions

Combining stellar abundances, ages, and orbital parameters, we will perform a stellar population and radial migration analysis to identify the Galactic regions of origin for the sample stars. This approach will allow us, for the first time, to investigate the variation of CNO enrichment as a function of Galactic radius across a large volume of the Milky Way. From the perspective of stellar evolution, precise abundance measurements and ages, together with activity indicators, will provide new insights into the effects of magnetic activity on stellar mixing processes, a topic that remains poorly understood.

These combined efforts will help clarify the complex interplay between stellar evolution and Galactic chemical enrichment, providing valuable constraints to refine models of both stellar and Galactic chemical evolution, and enhancing our understanding of the distribution of elements essential for life.

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